

ABSTRACT

By viewing world religions as shades of truth and examining etymologies, we cut God's Gordian knot.

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I. INTRODUCTION

If the LORD is all good, He would never mislead anyone, yet alone an entire group of people. Thus every religion on earth throughout history has legitimacy, best viewed as shades of grey. In the Bible there is a dichotomy between the Old Testament, the digital logic of the LORD's 10 Commandments, and the New Testament, Jesus's fuzzy logic of love.

If the Spirit of the LORD pervades everything inspiring people, then plausibly all people's best is of the LORD, and rigid cultural and linguistic differences are mute. Thus foremost we consider words of religious importance, and we create a course topology on them. Also history records the lives of eminent people, providing a testing ground for the legitimacy of reincarnation.

Our main premise is coincidence happens for a reason, and by examining the pattern this axiom implies, we prove the LORD exists. Approached differently, if coincidence has meaning on any set, then plausibly it does on all people's best. We group words according to similarity in: sound (despite independent linguistic roots), spelling, lexicality, meaning, and association. There is a consistent pattern of a trinity containing a ring and an emanation. Mathematically speaking, this paper loosely constructs topological graphs containing nonrandom patterns across languages.

II. IMAGE ETYMOLOGIES

IMAGE 1

Om Nama Narayana

ॐ नमो नारायणाय

Ring and Emanation

Fire and Water

"wheels were a burning fire" (Daniel 7:9), dharma

Yin-Yang, 巴 tomoe

陰 ("dark" → "negative force") + 陽 ("bright" → "positive force")

لَا إِلَهَ إِلَّا اللَّهُ

"There is no God but God"

IMAGE 2

Buddha

bud, seed, bulb (Genesis 40:10, Exodus 25:31-32)

(Sid)hartha (G)autama

Lord G.

Lord, loaf-ward, life-guard.

IMAGE 3

Infinite

in-finitus, not-finished

Lao-Tzu (L)i (E)r ... El

Master, Ahura Mazda, asteroid, Zoroaster.

Avestan: Zoroaster or Zaratuštra "he who can manage camels"

IMAGE 4

Father and Son

AND God Said

κύριε με ἐλέησον

ה' אלהיך יהוה אלהיך

'ehyeh 'āšer 'ehyeh

The Spirit of Detroit Statue

spirare + strait

blow + sund ... bubble, "bob and weave", "king of the ring"

"strait is the gate" (Matthew 7:14)

right is left (Acts 7:56)

Invictus "unconquered" poem, "veni vidi vici" Caesar

IMAGE 5
Whirlwind

(see books of Job and Esther)
hvirfill (circle) + Wend (sorb)
Spiral and Dot, "tie the knot"
Tower of Babel
Wizard and Dorothy of Oz
𐎧𐎺𐎠 Vizhi "Eye" and Δωροθέα "God's Gift" aka "Dot"
Egg of Ra

Sumerian: An (Sky) + Ki (Earth)
Enlil (Lord Wind, Ghost) + Enki (Lord Earth), also see Inanna/Ishtar
"wish upon a star", "star of wonder", asteroid (leading Magi)
wind, spin, spindle, dreidel
Ishtar, Ishara "oath", shard, Ishvara ईश्वर, Hera, Asherah "pole", Astarte, Esther, Easter "bunny" rabbit
Akkadian title rabītu "great lady", Hebrew rabbi "teacher" רַבִּי, lord رَّبٌّ

Ancient Greek:
Aether (Αἰθήρ) + Chaos (χάος) "void, gape, be wide open"
(O)uranos (Ουρανός) + (G)aia (Γαῖα)

Roman:
Gaius Julius Caesar + Cleopatra VII Philopator
Caelus Iulus Aesar + Κλεοπάτρα Φιλοπάτωρ (see the Aesir)
Sky Ilus Aether + "hear, glory, beloved of father"

Caesar assassinated Ides of March, sacred to Jupiter
Punic "elephant", a caesariē "because of the hair" (spin orientation), caedō "to cut" ritual duty of striking with the goat-skin

Adam + Lilith, and Eve (metaphorical garden of Eden, Sumerian edin "plain, steppe")
Adam bit the forbidden fruit (adultery), leading to broken rлaz (eyeball), glass (Jewish wedding)
apple ("apple of eye", Deuteronomy 32:10), "apple of discord" (for the fairest), apple bottom
Apep born of Ra's umbilical cord (Satan the Adversary), pome, pom-pom

Lilith (and Serpent), lilium convallium "lily of the valley" highly poisonous,
lilly pad (floating on water, lotus), ilium "hip bone", Illiad (Agamemnon + Helen), Lada (and Swan),
lili (Sumerian "female demon"), lilu (Akkadian "spirit"), illex (evergreen oak)

multicultural "tree of life", Yggdrasil "Odin's horse" meaning gallows, Buddha under Bhodi tree
"I am the bread of life" (John 6:35, compare Genesis 40:16-19)
"I am the true vine, and My Father is the vinedresser." (John 15:1, compare Genesis 40:9-11)

Note: Jesus's explicit mention of Caesar, Solomon, and Abraham in New Testament.
"Render to Caesear the things that are Caesar's; and to God the things that are God's." (Matthew 22:21)
"Observe how the lilies of the field grow; they do not toil nor do they spin, yet I say to you that even Solomon in all his glory did not clothe himself like one of these." (Matthew 6:28-29)
"Truly, truly, I say to you, before Abraham was born, I am." (John 8:58)

IMAGE 6
Genie of Lambda

Lamp, Biblical Lamb, Lambda, λ, El
Aladdin contains both genie of lamp and ring, hence
Lord of the Ring

Aladdin
('alā) عَالَاء + (ad-dīn) الدِّين
high, exalted + religion, way
Sumerian: elu "raise up" + di "to speak"

"ring of truth" (see John 14:6)
"ring a bell"
"belle of the ball"
"ball and chain"
"thread the needle"
"lightening and thunder"

"echoes in eternity"
በዘለለም ያስተጋባል
bezele'ālemi yasitegabali, bezel is border
Hallelujah and Hosanna

IMAGE 7
El of Biblos

Ba'alat Gebal, Lady of the Well, Lady G
Athirat "Lady Who Treads Upon the Sea", Jesus "walking on water"

Greek: βίβλος "book", βάλλω "to throw" (lightning)
Akkadian: Bāb-il "gate of God", Bēlu "lord"
Baal, ball, bell, belle

The LORD of Hosts
El who CREATED the Hosts

'el dū yahwī šaba'ôt
/כָּוֶן אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהִים

AL D YHWH SBAT
Host, Ghost, Господь (Lord), ... Eucharist
elephant, phantom

Bread of Life, Bubble leave, boil lief, bull leaf, blow love
bow and stern, prow and poop, bough steer, rainbow

"Yahweh and his Asherah", cow feeding its calf
'āšērâ אֲשֶׁרָה replaced with ἄσος "grove" or δένδρα "trees" in Bible
Asherah pole, Totem pole, Yule log, Christmas Tree with Orbs
Magi bring Jesus myrrh, frankincense, and gold, all obtainable from trees

reddish purple from Murex mollusc, Krishna's conch shell
Phoenicians, Phoenikkos of El, Phoenix, reincarnated firebird
Angels vs Devils (Thunderbirds vs Underwater Panthers)

The Lady of Shalott by Tennyson, Elaine (Ἑλένη) the lily maid of Astolat
Onion of Ashkelon, root ... Nikkal (Revelation 22:16)
"Beneath the moon, the reaper weary, ... Listening whispers, 'Tis the fairy" "
Jericho, Yarikh, Yareaḥ "moon", Jorah, Lord of the Sickle
Also Sword in the Stone, Ex-cali-bur ... obelisk, Egyptian tekhen

El, shell, scale, tile, Kali
pilaster (column, rod), pillar (Exodus 13:21), pill (ball), pilaf (rice ball)

elephant (Gautama, Gaius Caesar, Hannibal), ellipse (Gauss), epilepsy (Gaius Caesar),
elapse (time, pass, Passover, El Paso), eclipse (reap, corona)

eleos "mercy" Greek, eleph "ox" Phoenecian (alpha), elfet "swan" Old English,
felix "happy" Latin, phoenix, felis "cat" Latin, filius "son" Latin,
лис "fox" Russian, sly, lis (lilly, fleur-de-lis, flour), fleece (golden, lamb), flesh

quelle "source" German, γιλβα gilba sickle, ελενη (helene) "torch" Greek,
σεληνη (selene) "moon" Greek

IMAGE 8
Gandalf

G AND ALF (Mithra-ndir, Odin)
"Servant of Secret Fire"
Shepherd Dumuzid, Hurmuz, Ahura Mazda
"wielder of the flame of Anor" ... amor (love)

З огня огню (fire)
пара пара (water)
Бог Бога (God)
хмара хмара. (cloud casts shadow)

Ignite, fire, fȳr, ātar, ватра, ветер, pater, father, papi, pope, papyrus, папіроса, cigar
Vapour, пар, esper, espirare, esperanza, sphere, spire, spira, spirit
Holy, ямя, Yama, yam, whole, целий, цель, חגגס, hail (Caesar)
Chimera Χίμαιρα, Immaru "light" (Sumerian), Imrah ימרה "He Rebels",
marar מרר "bitter or strong", мрак "shadow", Umrah عُمْرَة "pilgrimage to Mecca",
mará 'death' मर, murder, morðor.

(M) - מ - mēm - water, meme "to imitate"
(M)hammad, (M)ecca, (M)edina, (M)uslim, (M)uhadeen, (M)osque
(M)etatron, (M)ary, Angra (M)ainu
Shadow, Hades, Shahadah [the Quran repeats]

Rod begat Lada, сердце радиться, влада родиться
(Avestan) Hvare-khshaeta "sun radiates", Hare Krishna हरे कृष्ण, ... rabbit
Agni + Svaha "well said", целий слова, цель слава
... श्रवस् sravas, स्वस्तिक swastika (tree, four Γ's, spin orientation)
श्री Shri, शिव Shiva "the Destroyer", אבדון Abbadon, Abba "Father", feather
самий один "yourself alone", Sammy Odin

IMAGE 9

Akira

明
 Sun and Moon
 Truth and Time (Father Time)
 Linear and Cyclic

Maat and Ptah
 Ra and Amun
 Hathor and Osiris
 Thor and Odin
 Zeus and Chronos (Zeus Georgos)
 Jove and Saturn (Sunday and Saturday)
 Juno and Jove
 Amaterasu and Tsukkuyomi

Yin-Yang and Shou
 Disc and Scarab
 Flail and Crook
 Rod and Ring (later Faravahar فروهار)
 Carrot and Stick (follow the white rabbit)
 Hare and Tortoise

Maat "righteousness", মে/মে "truth, justice", мати "mother", мать,
 Old Persian 𐎠𐎼𐎡𐎹 (mātā), māter (māter) "mother, source, origin"
 मातृ (matr) "mother", மாதா (Maathaa) "mother", மத (matha) "religious path"
 ... μέτρον (metron) "measure", meter, meteor

Ptah, Egypt, Hat-ka-ptah "temple of the soul of Ptah", πταχ "bird", Holy Ghost,
 Akkadian naptu, Old Persian *𐎱𐎠𐎴𐎡𐎹 (n-f-t /naft/), νάφθα naphtha "petroleum",
 नाथ (nātha) "LORD", पितृ (pitr) "father", Old Persian 𐎱𐎠𐎴𐎡𐎹 (pitā) [unleavened bread]

IMAGE 10

Q and G

𐤀 and 𐤂
 eye of needle and camel (Matthew 19:24)

Qi - Gong
 气 - 功

Spirit - Bell
 灵 - 铃
 ling ... rhymes with ring, king, cling (2 Kings 18:6, Jeremiah 13:11)
 Klinger anagrams Erl-King, Kringler

Sumerian: Qabu (speak) + Genii (spirits)
 Arabic: l-qayyum (the eternal) + l-hayyu (the alive)

Note: Q, L, M sources for the New Testament

IMAGES 11-16

M 1-6

lux "light" Latin, Луковна "daughter of Luka" Russian, лукавого "evil" Ukrainian

III. WORDS

Tort (injustice), torture, tortoise (Ancient ... of Days, and hare, Kobe), torque (twist), tor (anonymous internet, onion), tora (tiger), Torah, torrid (desert), torrent (flow), torpedo (electric ray), Toronto (wood in water), torment, tornado, torn (tear), thunder, Thor, toro (bull), Taurus, torus (doughnut), torii (Shinto gates), torr (pressure), tart (sour, unleavened), tartan (Tyrian, crisscross), Tartarus (abys), tarnation (damnation), tartaric (acid), Tartar (salt, Mongol), Tata (Father), tatters (rags), tattersall (checkered), tater (potato root), tatami (mat), tit-for-tat (an eye for an eye), tattle (speak), tarragon (Dragon), tartuffe (truffle root, fungus earth-ball, play mocking Catholic Church), tarsal (ankle), tarpaulin (mat), tarnish (silver, ... Tarshish), tarot (divination), taro (root), target, targe (shield), tarn (water hole), tarpon (jew-fish, Tarpon atlanticus), Targaryen (GOT), Tarrant (Coldfire Trilogy)

kale, cole (chou French), cauliflower (ball), kohlrabi, caulis (stem, stalk), callus, call, Kali (Devi), Kalevala, Calisto, Calypso, calendar (Caesar revised), calends (vs ides), calamari (pen, tako, taco), calf, Kafkaesque, Calcutta, Calabria (heel of Italy), Caleb (kelebh "dog"), caliber (shell), Caliban (beast), caul (fetal membrane), caudal (tail), caudillo (dictator), calamine (calamus "reed"), calamity, calash (kolo "wheel"), recalcitrant, calcaneus "heel-bone," Latin calx "heel" perhaps Etruscan. Old Prussian culczi "hip," Lithuanian kulkšnis "ankle-(bone)," Bulgarian kalka "hip, thigh", callipygian (buttocks), kallos "beauty" Greek, khalessi (GOT)

shell, skalja "tile" Gothic, scaglia "chip" Italian, skal "cup" Old Norse, skaal "dish" West Frisian, schale "pod" German, skala "splinter, to cut" Lithuanian, скала "rock" Old Church Slavonic, halë ("splinter") Albanian, कल (kalá, "small part") Sanskrit, iškalla ("to tear apart, slit open") Hittite, skélti ("to split") Lithuanian, σκάλλω (skállō, "to hoe, harrow") Ancient Greek, искал ("search") Russian

scale, shale, shall (Thou), shallop (boat), shallot (onion, Lady), s-hallow, shalom, shellac (plaster), shelter, shield, shekel (silver), sheikh

shale anagrams:

hales ("hollow"), sahel (سَاهِل sāhil, "border of the desert" Arabic), saleh (صَالِح sâleh "pious" Persian), salah (سَلَاة salah, "to hang", implying "to weigh", "to measure" Biblical Hebrew), haless (health, whole, upright, rock), halse ("neck, prow of a ship"), heals, leash, salah (سَلَاة pause), sheal (shell, pod)

Logic (Gauss), logistic (Gaius), Logos (Gautama), logi ("flame" Old Norse), lodge (shelter, Masonic), logo (sign), loggerhead (large carnivorous turtle), logger (fell trees, input data), logarithm (base 10), log (knots, fags), loft ("sky" Old English, luftus "air" Gothic, louft "bark" Old High German), -logy (treatise, theory), loimic (plague)

gauge (rod, judge), Gaul (Caesar), Gautama, Gauss, gauntlet, gate, ... Gaia (earth), Gayatra (sun)

Christ, crust, crest, crescent, croissant, akris "locust" Greek, κρύσταλλος krystallos "ice" Ancient Greek, khriein (annoint), crane, Krishna (elephant), Eucharist

crikey (Christ), cringe (German Kring "circle, ring"), Cringle (Kris Kringle, Santa Claus), crinoid (Greek krinoeides "lily-like"), cripes (Christ), criss-cross (Chess), crocodile, crocus (saffron Buddhist Robes), Cronus, crook (shepherd's, and flail), crop (reap), croquet (hoop and ball), cross

Church (cirice Old English, kirika Old Saxon, kyrios "lord" Greek, ... circle, Greek kirkos "ring")

Wind, win, window (border), windage (ring), whirlwind, Winchester (won West, shells), periwinkle (spiral), wander, wand (Old Norse vandr "rod")

quixotic (Don Quixote, latin coxa "hip" de la mancha "spot"), quey (young cow, kviga Old Norse), Quetzalcoatl (plumed serpent god, quetzal "tail-feather"+ coatl "snake"), Q'uq'umatz, quest, quesadilla (queso "cheese" Spanish), quern (stone mill, kvern Old Norse), Quercus "oak" Latin (Albuquerque), quell (quellian "to torture, kill" Old Saxon), Quechua (Peruvian, Quechua kechua "destroyer" Inca), Quebec ("strait, narrows" Micmac Algonquian), queasy (kveisa "boil" Old Norse), quay (key, keye, caye "wharf" Middle English from cai, chai, quai "sand bank" French, from caium Gaulish, *kagio- "to encompass, enclose" Old Celtic, Welsh cae "fence, hedge" ... Caesar), Quasimodo (hunchback of Notre Dame), quasar (quasi-stellar), quash

mitre (turban, Bishop's hat), מִצְנֶפֶת mitznefet (High Priest of Israel), μίτρα band, mitra (friend) Sanskrit, Mithra (God of contract) Avestan, Mithrandir (Gandalf), mithril (silver), Mithras (Persian god of sun)

hare (rabbit), harry (strife), hari (Rama hari Krishna), hairy (Caesar), hair-ball, cross-hair, hakim "wise" Arabic, hakam "judge" Arabic, Hakenkreuz (hook-cross German, swastika), halal (lawful), halberd (pole), halcyon (peaceful, bird, halb "salt" + kyon "conceiving" ... cumulus cloud), hale (healthy, Proto-Germanic *halon "to call," PIE root *kele- to shout), hail (ball, Caesar), half (halb "divide" German), halo (ring, ... aura, glory), Hallstatt ("place of salt" Austrian), hallow (saint), hallelujah, hall (temple), hell, Haliastur (Alexel, KC), hole

Colonel, colt (camel, revolver), coronel, corona (ring of sun), cornea (ring of eye), coroner, crown, corolla, король (king)

kernel, carne "flesh" Spanish, kerosene, kerygma (preaching), kardia (heart), cardinal (bird), core, corgi (dog), corium (Latin skin), кора (bark), quercus (oak), cortex (cerebral), cornu (horn, spiral), cornea (ring), cornel (cherry tree), chorus, carol, khoros "round dance", chorion (outer membrane of fetus), Chronos

scarab, scar, scare, scarlet, scarf, scorch, scoff, scathe, scapula (spade, triangle, delta)

goat, goal "boundary, limit", gale "way, wind", gaule "long pole, stake" Old French, ... Gaul, goad "spear", ... God, gadfly "stinger", gae "spear" Old Irish, gad "make haste", gard "rod" Dutch, gaddr "spike, nail, rod" Old Norse, gar "pike fish", *gaisa- "spear" Proto-Germanic, ... Gaius, garlic "onion like bulbous plant", gore (blood, triangle of earth), Gordian knot, gorge "swallow, whirlpool", George, gorgeous, Gorgias (Greek sophist), gorgon (turn to stone), gare "shelter", gargle "bubble", gargoyle, garland "wreath"

see (holy), seer, sire, sir, Osiris (iris and pupil), Sirius ("dog star"), Sirion (Mount Hermon), see, seed, seat, seek, seizure (epileptic), set (theory, Hebrew seth "appointed", Egyptian Setesh, god of war, chaos, storms, loss of testicle, protector of Ra, defeats Apep), PIE *sed- "to sit" ... сидити, sedeo, Seder (Passover), cedar (Lebanon), cider (apple), sedum (flower), insidious, cid (Lord), sayyed, siddha सिद्ध, sith, ... scythe, sitar, ... star, siddha (saint), acid (tart)

shin (22 letter of Hebrew alphabet, the End), Shin Bet (Israeli security service), shingle (tile, scale), Shinola (Swiss watch in Detroit, shoe polish), Shinto (shin "god, gods, spirit" + tao "way, path, doctrine"), shine, ship, shape

pal "to know" Hurrian, palm (hamsa), palmer (impoverished monk), palomino (young dove), palpable (felt, touch), palsgrave (count), palter (babble), palatine (quasi-royal, Caesar), Palpatine (Star Wars), paladin (... Aladdin), palooka (prizefighter), paludal (marsh, 5or)

minx (mynx "pet dog," wanton pert girl, Min of WOT, Minnie Driver in GWH and GPB, minsk "man" Low German, mensch "wench, child, maid"), minnesinger (minne "sexual love"), minion, minor, Minoan (Cretan, liar, Christian), minnow (small fish, sardine), Minnesota (cloudy water), minister (vs magister, master), mink (vs muskrat), minstrel, menique (Pinky), mind

Turan "mistress, lady" Etruscan, Turandot (opera by Puccini), Tyrrhenian "Etruscan", tyrsis "tower" Greek, tyro "young soldier" tiro Latin, Tyrol (Austro-Hungarian province bordering Grisons' goat), tir "land", Celtic terra "earth" Latin, tyrant, Tyre (tire, rim), Tyrannosaurus Rex (sauros "lizard", saulos "twisting" Greek)

Sanskrit, Santa Claus, sap (sappa "spade"), sapient (Old English sefa "mind"), sapling, saponify (turn to soap), Sapphire (Sanskrit sanipriya from Sani "Saturn" + priyah "precious"), sappy, Saracen (Arabic sharq "east, sunrise"), Saran (PVC cling film), Sauron, sarcasm (Greek sarkos "flesh"), sardine, sardonic (laughter then death), sarin, shard

chime (Middle English as chymbe bellen, SET of BELLS tuned to musical SCALE), Cymbal, symbol. Chime anagrams (hemic "BLOOD" from Greek αἷμα haîma, AND French miche "leavened round LOAF", also "buns, bum, butt" from Latin mīca "crumb")

sylvan (Latin silva "wood, forest", ... silver, sliver), sylph (air spirit, silf anagram flis, Greek silphe "a kind of beetle", Greek nymph, ... self, sleeve "divide"), syllogism (proof), Sydney (Cid "Lord" Arabic)

orb, orbis (Earth, circle), orbital, orchid (Greek "testicle" root), orphan, orbe (Irish "heir"), ierfa (Old English "heir"), arbeit (work), arbitrage, arbiter "judge"

cochineal (scarlet berry insect), cocci (spherical bacteria), Greek kokkos "grain, seed, berry", cocoon (shell), cock (bird), coco (palm tree), cacao (seed), coca (Inca plant), coccyx (tailbone), cochlea (spiral cavity of inner ear), conch (shell), Viracocha (God, literally "sea foam" Inca), rocca ("stone" Latin)

talon "finger", talus (Latin "ankle"), talea (Latin "rod"), taxillus (Latin "die, cube"), tallow "hard animal fat, used to make soap", tassel "border, fringe", tailor "cut", telos "end", talk, tale, talanton "scale", tālib (Arabic "student"), Talmud (Hebrew lamadh "he learned")

Neo, new, nue (French "cloud"), nubes (Latin "cloud"), noubti (Coptic "to weave"), nub (Nubian "gold"), nubia (French "woman's light scarf"), obnubere (Latin "veil"), snaoda (Avestan "clouds"), nuance (shade), Neva ("wet swamp, bog" Finnish)

Gold, gull (shore bird), geld (tax), γιλθα gilpa sickle, золото, Xolotl (dog head)

aura, taurus, aurochs (bull like), orage (thunderstorm), aureus (gold), oracle, laurel, honor, hour, samurai, Varuna, Ouranos

Islam (submission), aslama (give oneself to God), salaam (peace), shalom (peace), Lama (guru), llamada ("call" Spanish), ulama (hip-ball, see illium), ulema (Muslim scholars)

AOM, AO, TAO, LOAF, OATH, GOAT, SOAP, YOGA, MOAI, CHAOS, PHARAOH

Om, omni, omen, ominous, OMega, Ōmeteōtl, Aum, Amun-Ra, Amen

ALF, אֵלֶף, 𐤀, ألف, ἄλφα, elf, self, calf, half, Aleph Egyptian vulture hieroglyph, single "reed" hieroglyph, Phoenician 'āleph "ox", Modern Hebrew Alef "general", see "One thousand and one nights"

bliss, blister, blizzard, blaze, bleach (Old English noun blæce "leprosy"), bleak (Old English blæc "black"), blanche

Luke, lucky, lux (Latin "light"), lox (salmon), lucre (riches), Lucy (LSD, acid), Loki (Old Norse "tangler")

Hadad, Adad aka Rammanu "Thunderer", Aramaic 𐤇𐤏𐤍𐤐 Ra^ḥmā, Hebrew: 𐤇𐤏𐤍 Ra^ḥam. Rama, ram, drama, dream, frame, Ramadan, громіть (thunder)

Ab (Hebrew אב "father"), absolute, abstract, astral (Greek star, anagrams altars, tarsal), asteroid, astray (dog), Alistair (Alexander), disaster, destroy, easter, beast, East, coaster (disc)

Adonai, אֲדֹנָי (sir, lord), ad (Ugaritic 𐎠𐎡 ad "father"), Adam, adamant, adamare ("love" Latin), adamu (Akkadian "to make"), ... Ātman आत्मन्, Atum ("finish" Egyptian god), atmen ("breath" German)

wicked (wick), succubus (cubit), siren (sire)

Shiva, Siva (Samoan dance, fire circles), sieve (Passover)

Zen (circle enso), Zenon, Zeus, Deus

author, arthur, authority, Thor

excalibur, kali, caliph, kylix (Greek: cup), Izcalli (18th month Aztec calendar), искал ("search") Russian, колесо (wheel), колокол (bell), calyx (and corolla of a flower)

wise, wizard, вижу, vizier, vizard (conceal), viçira (Avestan "arbitrator"), vici

rain, sovereign, ray, radix (10), rei

Aztec, Aztlan, Aslan, Atlantis, Atlas, τάλαιος talas "wretched", Tantalus, tantra (तन्त्र, weave)

Salt, psalm, alms, пса (dog), сало (fat), Cuezaltzin

Sol, sole, soul, soil, солонго "rainbow", Solomon

Ball, Baal, Baalat, ballein (Greek "throw"), ebullient, boil, billiard, bull, bullet (shell), bulla (Latin "bubble"), Bellum (Latin "war"), bell, belle, belt, Shambhala (शम्भल, वनेवसु)

spike, pike, splinter, spoke, spake, spin, spit (rod), spica (star, "ear of grain")

Caesar, Aesir, ether, ester, jester, Esther (Persian sitareh "star"), eternal, keter (Hebrew קֶטֶר keter "Crown"), atar (Zoroastrian holy fire), avatāra अवतार, water, ватера, витер, pater, mater

Qi, key, Caesar, quay (border), quasar

rim, rime (manna), rhyme, rind, ring

Manat, mana, manna, Immanuel

Messier (reaper), Messiah

Bell (Gaussian) curve

Calibrate (Set)

ring, ringer, baller

cross, passover

Rubicon (cross)

God anagram dog ... dogma, good, gold

Cali, Ali

(Mast)er, Rod, Rodin (Thinker at Gates of Hell), Aphrodite, prodigy

Odin, один (One), ordinal (Set theory), ordinance (10X), wodin, wod (mad), wood, Godan "Master", God, pagoda

cyclic, sickle, sick, ill, seek

Rabbit, раб (slave)

strife, strive (israel)

Bhagavad-Gita, Бора Guitar, "God's Song"

Math (Old English mæð "mowing, cutting of grass," ... source also of Old Frisian meth, Old High German mad ... to reap, also Greek manthanein "to learn")

Finance ("an end, SETTlement, retribution", compare Greek telos "end", Latin finis "that which divides, boundary, limit, border, end" hence "acme, peak, height", Old French fin "end, limit, boundary; death; fee, payment, finance, money"), fine ("true, genuine; faithful, constant"), finish ("surface, polish", Latin finire "to limit, SET bounds; put an end to; come to an end," related to Latin figere "to fasten, fix", with fix "SET, settle, assign, arrange, repair, make permanent, fasten, castrate, hole, dose, take vengeance"), Finnish (Norsemen's name for the Suomi, Sami, Russian сам "alone", Arabic سَامِيّ sāmiyy, "exalted", village of Sämi in eastern Switzerland, also Lapp anagram palp "fleshy part of fingertip", diminutive of Samuel Hebrew "name of God" also "death", Old English fenn "marsh, bog, border between land and water" ... marshal, Бор)

taro root in Japan with "elephant ear" leaves, κολοκασσι "lotus root", lámbo in Yoruba, kalo in Hawaii, talo in Samoan, ta'o in Marquesan, tales in Javanese, bal in Manipur, aba in Philippines, 芋頭 (ō-á) in Taiwan, dalo in Fijian, toran 토란 "earth egg" in Korea, arbi in Urdu and Hindi, Patra in Gujarat, bäl in Mizoram, ghandyali in Himachal, patra in Shimla, saru in Odisha, sivapan-kizhangu in Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh, ala in Maldives, pindalu in Nepal, eddoe in Pakistan and Suriname, kolakana ala in Sri Lanka, inhame-coco in Portugal, cocoyam in Nigeria, Ghana and Cameroon, acra in Haiti, callaloo in Trinidad and Tobago, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, and Dominica. Consider Torah, tora 虎 "tiger".

IV. ARCHANGELS

Judaism - Menorah, Christianity - Archangels, Zoroastrianism - six great Amesha Spenta, literally "Bounteous/Holy Immortals" of Ahura Mazda

Travis (crossroad, anagram: सवित् savitr sun), Ravi (sun), raven, traverse (pass over), transverse, trave (crossbeam), travertine (rock), travail (to torture)

Flis (sliver Old Norse "to cut", splinter, chip, ... silver), (tile German, cubit (elbow, ell), qubit, sounds like till (limit, end, soil, strive, cashbox), tail (root, wick), tale (recount, number), plate, disc, ring, record, graph, Γραφ, Count, Taira, tiara, to lay brick (GWH), Tyler Durden (FC), tessellation, tesseract, Rubik's Cube, Rubicon, to optimize a loop, doorkeeper at Masonic lodge, stiff hat, καλυμμαύχιον)(fleece Czech, Golden), (raftsman Polish, Charon's obol, transports logs to sawmill, Logician)

Anna, ankh (tau cross with an oval loop at the top, Egyptian symbol of life, Egyptian ankh, literally "life, soul"), anklet (ring), anneal (Old English onælan "set on fire, kindle; inspire, incite"), anulus "little ring" Latin, annihilate, Hannah (Hebrew "grace", biblical mother of prophet Samuel), Hannibal (Punic Hannibha'al literally "my favor is with Baal", Hebrew Ba'al "master, lord"), hansom (cab), Hanukkah (Hebrew "consecration", menorah, lamp burned for 7 days using one day's oil)

Mary "rebellion", Miriam, "Mary had a little lamb whose fleece was white as snow", marionette "puppet on strings", gun moll "female criminal" (gonif "thief"), Miss Molly had a Polly, pollard (de-horned animal), polliwog (tadpole, larval frog), Mari anagram Amir "Prince"

Musk (father Errol or Earl, Count), Brother Kimbal, Kimberly (see Eminem) muska-s "testicle", mosca "fly", mosquito, musket (compare dragoon, falcon), mousquette (sparrow-hawk), muskeg (bog, Бог or God), Muskegon (Michigan), muskrat (beaver, engineer), Muscovy, мозг (brain), Muscat (hidden), mussel (murex, purple), Mosaic

marrowsky (wordplay), Mars (Ares of war), Marsala (Arabic Mirsa-llahi, "the Port of God"), Marseilles ("spring", Massilia, make soap), marsh (swamp, bog, Бог or God), marshal (Mathers, Maedere "reaper", Mathers, Haley ... hale, ex-wife Kimberly. E-min-em: Infinite, 8-Mile, Psalms of David), marshmallow (LOTR: althaea "to heal")

Soros formerly Schwartz (son Alexander), cirrhosis (inflammation of liver), kirros (red-yellow), kyrios (Lord), circus "ring", kirkos "a circle, a ring", cire (wax, polish, Sire), cirrus (fleecy clouds), cirrous (bud), Sirius "the Dog Star", Seirios "scorching" Greek, psoriasis (scaly disease), sōros "heap of corn" reaped Greek.

Schwartz "black" German, sword "cut", swear, swathe (wrap), swath (cut by scythe), swat, swastika (luck), swart (Old English sweart "black", "dark clouds", "wick-ed, infamous"), sordid (fester), sore (seer Middle Dutch), sorcerer (Latin sors "lot, fate, fortune"), sorrel "reddish brown", sear "withered, barren", sour (Old English sur "sour, tart, acid, fermented", German säure "acid" German, Russian сырой "moist, raw", сыр "cheese" ... queso Spanish, Latin caeseus, ... Caesar), sūras "salty" Lithuanian, Tyre (/ˈtaɪər/, "rock", Arabic صور Šūr, Phoenician ʿṣ Šūr, Lebanese French Sour), Sūrah (chapter of Qar'an), sorghum "Indian millet", sorrow, Sauron (LOTR, eye)

Putin, путь (path, way), спутник (satellite, moon), распутье (crossroads), Vladimir (vlasti "to rule over" + miru "peace"), Lada, мир (peace, piece, world, cosmos, space station satellite), *mei "to bind, tie", смею "laugh", Sanskrit smerah "smiling" (sickle), miracle, mirror (glass), Miryam (peace Yama), mire (bog, Бог), mirage, mirth, merry, мирячить (epileptic)

Samael = Hebrew Shemiel from Ha-Shem "the name" + El "God", Samael "death, destroyer" partner of Lilith, Grim Reaper with scythe, Sama-El or Lord El in Japanese.

Samuel anagrams: amelus (foetus born without limbs), émulas (French "to emulate"), musela (French "to muzzle, silence"), muséal ("of museums"), salume (Italian bal-oney sausage), ulemas (Arabic عَالِم 'ālim "learned one")

Michael = Hebrew "Who is like El?", Saint Michael the Taxiarch (Greek ταξιάρχος "brigadier" from táxis "order" ... Thurn and Taxis), Prince of Heavenly Host, treading on a dragon (Satan), with sword and scales, patronage police and military, protector of Jews and guardian of Catholics, patron saint of Germany, on coat of arms of Kyiv, Ukraine, prominent in Eastern Orthodox Christianity.

Helel = Hebrew "bright, lucent, shiny", also Yahoel, also Lucifer Latin lux "light"+ ferre "to carry", Hebrew Satan "adversary", Greek diabolos "slanderer" from diaballein "to throw across," Beelzebub Hebrew ba'al-z'bul "lord of the flies", Metatron μετὰ θρόνου meta thronos "over, across" + "throne", Islamic Mīṭatrūn (Arabic: ميططرون), the angel of the veil (Latin velum "curtain", conceal, disguise, sail), highest of the angels, celestial scribe or recording angel, Chancellor of Heaven. Depicted in the Daqa'iq al-Haqa'iq (دقائق الحقائق "Degrees of Truths") by Nasir ad-Din Rammal 14th century CE.

Uriel or Auriel = Hebrew "Light of God", carrying celestial orb or disc of stars and constellations, in Longfellow's Golden Legend the angel of Mars.

Jophiel = Hebrew "beauty of God", also Zophiel לַפִּי'עַל Šōfi'ēl, "spy, watchman of God", patronage artists, illumination and exposure of wrongdoing, right hand flaming sword left sceptre (of a marshal), statue at Mundelein Center for performing arts, Loyola University, Chicago.

Gabriel = Hebrew "God is my Strength", "to gab", patronage telecommunication workers, radio broadcasters, messengers, diplomats, ambassadors, beautiful statues in Budapest.

Raphael = Hebrew "God has healed", patronage healing, Angel of the Trumpet, particular enemy of the devil, in Book of Tobit Raphael guides and aides Tobias.

V. COMPANY NAMES

Automotive Companies:

Mazda (Ahura)
Lexus (L)
Lada, лада
Infinity
GM
Ford (crossing)
Chrysler
Alfa Romeo
Lotus
Lamborghini
Genesis
Isuzu (Isa)
Tesla (tesselation)
Ferrari (bull)
Audi 4 rings
Toyota ellipses
Subaru stars
Buick shields

Models:

Toyota Corolla
Jeep Rubicon
Mitsubishi Eclipse Cross
Buick Lacrosse
Chrysler GT, 300
Ford Taurus
Dodge Ram
Hyundai Elantra
Chevrolet Silverado
Cadillac Escalade
Kia Sorento
Buick Terraza
VW Tiguan (Guanyin)

Companies:

Soros' (Q)uantum Fund (Hedge Fund)
Alden Shoes (Aladdin)
Brooks Brothers (Golden Fleece)
Ralph Lauren Polo (Alpha Aura Pole)
Tor Fantasy
LG
Shell Oil
Belle Tire
QL Quicken Loans
Little Caesar's
U of (M)ichigan (Hail)

VI. WORLD MEDIA

Great Teacher Onizuka (anime):

Eikichi Onizuka as "Genie of the Lamp" (Episode 17)

Urumi Kanzaki as "Sadako" of Ring, rose from "dead", cross on helmet.

(M)elkor (LOTR), (M)aijin-Buu (Dragonball), (M) (James Bond)

Q (Star Trek), Q (James Bond)

FF7

The Pinky and the Brain

South Park

Beauty and the Beast

Peter Pan

Atlantis

Tifa and Cloud (anagram fiat "word" John 1:1, Exodus 16:10)

Pinky and Brain

Jesus and Cartman

Belle and Beast

Tinkerbell and Peter Pan

Kida and Milo

Hercules

Aladdin

Megara (Job) and Hercules

Jasmine (Buddha's wife Yaśodharā) and Aladdin

The Silver Chair

The Lord of the Rings

Akira

Oldboy

Natural Born Killers

Fight Club

The Matrix

Vanilla Sky

Good Will Hunting

Star Wars

John Wick

GP Blank

Books:

Sword of Truth

Wheel of Time

Coldfire Trilogy

Kingkiller Chronicle

Game of Thrones

The Count of Monte Cristo

(Jagang "Dreamwalker" and Richard Rahl "War Wizard")

(Min and Rand Al'Thor)

(Calesta and Tarrant)

(Haliax aka Alexel and the Chandrian)

(Jon Snow)

VII. REINCARNATION

Q:

Adam (died ~2800)
Gilgamesh (died ~2600)
Abraham (died 1975)
Joseph (died 1445)
Tutankhamun (1341-1323)
Agamemnon (about 1250-1180)
Samson (between 1127-1070)
Solomon (990-931)
Li Er (8-7th century)
Zoroaster (628-551)
Sun Tzu (544-496)
Gautama Siddhartha (480-400)
Diogenes (404-323)
Hannibal (247-181)
Gaius Julius Caesar (100-44 BCE)
Judas Iscariot (?-30 CE)
Marcus Aurelius (121-180)
St. Francis of Assisi (1181-1226)
Cosimo de Medici (1389-1464)
Wayna Qhapaq (1468-1524)
Ivan the Terrible (1530-1584)
Musashi Miyamoto (1584-1645)
Carl Friedrich Gauss (1777-1855)
Charles Alexander Eastman (1858-1939)
John Lennon (1940-1980)

Notable:

bit metaphorical apple, broken glass
master of animals, searching, spurned Inanna
almost sacrificed son, ring scar circumcision
goat blood, vizier, wheat reaper
"living image of Amun", 18th dynasty
House Atreus, Tantalus sacrificed son
Hebrew שִׁמְשׁוֹן , Šimšōn, "man of the sun"
"peaceful", Ecclesiastes "under the sun"
the Tao
Avestan "he who can manage camels"
the Art of War
elephant dream of mother Maya
cynic, debased currency, admired dog
collected rings of dead Romans, elephants
epilepsy, dictator, Ides of March, ring at Alesia
scarab, silver coins, almost sacrificed Jesus
stoic, reduced silver purity
bird in hand, master of animals, stigmata
arms 6 balls and fleur de lis, tomb ring
grain silos, astronomical observatory
killed son under mercury poisoning
Book of 5 Rings
elliptic orbits, studied curvature
Ohíye S'a, Dakota: "always wins"
the Beatles, assassinated at the Dakota

G:

Lilith (died ~2800)
Helen of Troy (13th century)
Absalom (flourished 1020)
Jezebel (died 842)
Esther (5-4th century)
Cleopatra of Egypt (69-30)
Jesus of Nazareth (4 BCE-30 CE)
Sacagawea (1788-1812)
Lilly Langtree (1853-1929)

Notable:

beauty, "mythological" partners Adam and Samael
beauty, adulteress, killed by hanging from tree
beauty, usurper, killed hanging from tree
influence, usurper, fags did not ignite, eaten by dogs
beauty, saving Hebrews, "half of the kingdom", gallows
beauty, usurper, dressed as Isis, suicide via asp
influence, usurper, crucified, prophet, Son of God
guided L&C Expedition at 16, Hidatsa "Bird Woman"
beauty, endorsed soap, enjoyed yachts and horse racing

M:

Eve (died ~2800)
Mary of Nazareth (18 BCE-after 30CE)
Muhammad (570-632)
Mozart Wolfgang Amadeus (1756-1791)

Notable:

khavá חָוָה Hebrew and "snake" חַוִּי Old Aramaic
husband Joseph, immaculate conception like Isaac
Kaaba contains meteorite of Adam and Eve
loved elegant clothing

Job of Uz (around 2000 BCE, after Abraham)

"But I would speak to the Almighty,
And I desire to argue with God." (Job 13:3)

"For there is hope for a tree,
When it is cut down, that it will sprout again,
And its shoots will not fail.
Though its roots grow old in the ground,
And its stump dies in the dry soil,
At the scent of water it will flourish
And put forth sprigs like a plant.
But man dies and lies prostrate.
Man expires, and where is he?
... If a man dies, will he live again?" (Job 14:7-14)

"How often is the lamp of the wicked put out,
Or does their calamity fall on them?
Does God apportion destruction in His anger?
Are they as straw before the wind,
And like chaff which the storm carries away?
You say, 'God stores away a man's iniquity for his sons.'
Let God repay him so that he may know it.
Let his own eyes see his decay,
And let him drink of the wrath of the Almighty." (Job 21:17-20)

"Behold, I go forward but He is not there,
And backward, but I cannot perceive Him;
When He acts on the left, I cannot behold Him;
He turns on the right, I cannot see Him.
But He knows the way I take;
When He has tried me, I shall come forth as gold." (Job 23:8-10)

"Then the LORD answered Job out of the whirlwind and said,
Who is this that darkens counsel
By words without knowledge?
Now gird up your loins like a man,
And I will ask you, and you instruct Me!
Where were you when I laid the foundation of the earth?" (Job 38:1-4)

"Behold now, Behemoth, which I made as well as you; ...
He is confident, though the Jordan rushes to his mouth." (Job 40:15-23)

"Then all his brothers, and all his sisters, and all who had known him before, came to him, and they ate bread with him in his house; and they consoled him and comforted him for all the evil that the LORD had brought on him. And each one gave him one piece of money, and each a ring of gold." (Job 42:11)

Delilah (between 1127-1070 BCE)

"Then she said to him, 'How can you say, "I love you," when your heart is not with me? You have deceived me these three times and have not told me where your great strength is.' And it came about when she pressed him daily with her words and urged him, that his soul was annoyed to death. So he told her all that was in his heart and said to her, 'A razor has never come on my head, for I have been a Nazirite to God from my mother's womb. If I am shaved, then my strength will leave me and I shall become weak and be like any other man.'" (Judges 16:15-17)

Caesar's barber (between 100-44 BCE)

"Caesar was first captivated by this proof of Cleopatra's bold wit, and was afterwards so overcome by the charm of her society that he made a reconciliation between her and her brother, on condition that she should rule as his colleague in the kingdom.

A festival was kept to celebrate this reconciliation, where Caesar's barber, a busy listening fellow, whose excessive timidity made him inquisitive into everything, discovered that there was a plot carrying on against Caesar by Achilles, general of the king's forces, and Pothinus, the eunuch. Caesar, on the first intelligence of it, set a guard upon the hall where the feast was kept and killed Pothinus." (Plutarch's Life of Caesar)

Uriel: Leonardo da Vinci

- polymath, engineer
- educated in Florence, once sponsored by Medici clan
- conceptualized flying machines, a type of armored fighting vehicle, concentrated solar power, an adding machine, and double hull
- earliest memory of flying kite recorded in codex Atlanticus, large leaves used for atlases
- painted a round shield with head of Medusa ("guardian") the Gorgon, not used but replaced with shield with arrow in heart motif, Cupid
- sketch of the hanging of Baroncelli
- study for Leda and the Swan
- once decorated a lizard with scales dipped in quicksilver
- mechanical lion struck on chest by wand revealed lilies
- habit of purchasing caged birds and releasing them
- painted Salvator Mundi, Mona Lisa, Madonna and Saint Anne
- contemporaries Michaelangelo, Raphael

VIII. RELEVANT PASSAGES

Genesis 19:24-26 "Then the LORD rained on Sodom and Gomorrah brimstone and fire from the LORD out of heaven, and He overthrew those cities, and all the valley, and all the inhabitants of the cities, and what grew on the ground. But his [Lot's] wife, from behind him, looked back; and she became a pillar of salt."

Genesis 37:5-9 "Then Joseph had a dream, and when he told it to his brothers, they hated him even more. And he said to them, 'Please listen to this dream which I have had; for behold, we were binding sheaves in the field, and lo, my sheaf rose up and also stood erect; and behold, your sheaves gathered around and bowed down to my sheaf.' Then his brothers said to him, 'Are you actually going to reign over us? Or are you really going to rule over us?' So they hated him even more for his dreams and for his words. Now he had still another dream, and related it to his brothers, and said, 'Lo, I have had still another dream; and behold, the sun and the moon and eleven stars were bowing down to me.'"

Genesis 40:9-11 "So the chief cupbearer told his dream to Joseph, and said to him, 'In my dream, behold, there was a vine in front of me; and on the vine were three branches. And as it was budding, its blossoms came out, and its clusters produced ripe grapes. Now Pharaoh's cup was in my hand; so I took the grapes and squeezed them into Pharaoh's cup, and I put the cup into Pharaoh's hand.'"

Genesis 40:16-19 "When the chief baker saw that he had interpreted favorably, he said to Joseph, 'I also saw in my dream, and behold, there were three baskets of white bread on my head; and in the top basket there were some of all sorts of baked food for Pharaoh, and the birds were eating them out of the basket on my head.' Then Joseph answered and said, 'This is its interpretation: the three baskets are three days; within three more days Pharaoh will lift up your head from you and will hang you on a tree; and the birds will eat your flesh off you.'"

Exodus 7:3 "But I will harden Pharaoh's heart that I may multiply My signs and My wonders in the land of Egypt."

Exodus 15:3
"The LORD is a warrior;
The LORD is His name."

Leviticus 16:21 "Then Aaron shall lay both of his hands on the head of the live goat, and confess over it all the iniquities of the sons of Israel ... and send it away into the wilderness"

Leviticus 23:39 "On exactly the fifteenth day of the seventh month, when you have gathered in the crops of the land, you shall celebrate the feast of the LORD for seven days" (Ides)

Numbers 22:28 "And the LORD opened the mouth of the donkey, and she said to Balaam, 'What have I done to you, that you have struck me these three times?' "

Numbers 28:16-17 "On the fourteenth day of the first month shall be the LORD's Passover. And on the fifteenth day of this month shall be a feast, unleavened bread shall be eaten for seven days." (Ides)

Deuteronomy 21:23 "he who is hanged is accursed of God"

Joshua 6:4 "Seven priests shall carry seven trumpets of rams' horns before the ark; then on the seventh day you shall march around the city seven times"

Joshua 10:11 "the LORD threw large stones from heaven on them as far as Azekah, and they died; there were more who died from the hailstones than those whom the sons of Israel killed with the sword."

Joshua 10:13 "So the sun stood still, and the moon stopped"

Judges 6:37 "fleece of wool"

Judges 7:5 "You shall separate everyone who laps the water with his tongue, as a dog laps"

Judges 7:7 "I will deliver you with the 300 men who lapped"

1 Samuel 3:10 "Samuel! Samuel!"

2 Samuel 18:9 "Absalom was riding on his mule, and the mule went under the thick branches of a great oak. And his head caught fast in the oak, so he was left hanging between heaven and earth, while the mule that was under him kept going."

1 Kings 10:14 "Now the weight of gold which came in to Solomon in one year was 666 talents of gold."

2 Kings 9:22 "the harlotries of your mother Jezebel and her witchcrafts are so many"

1 Chronicles 22:10 "He [Solomon] shall build a house for My name, and he shall be My son, and I will be his father; and I will establish the throne of his kingdom over Israel forever."

2 Chronicles 9:17-19 "The king [Solomon] made a great throne of ivory and overlaid it with pure gold. And there were six steps to the throne and a footstool in gold attached to the throne, and arms on each side of the seat, and two lions standing beside the arms. And twelve lions were standing there on the six steps on the one side and on the other; nothing like it was made for any other kingdom."

Esther 9:21-26 "celebrate the fourteenth day of the month Adar, and the fifteenth day of the same month, annually, because on those days the Jews rid themselves of their enemies ... they called these days Purim" (Ides)

Isaiah 2:3-4

"For the law will go forth from Zion,
And the word of the LORD from Jerusalem.
And He will judge between the nations,
And will render decisions for many peoples;
And they will hammer their swords into plowshares, and their spears into pruning hooks.
Nation will not lift up sword against nation,
And never again will they learn war."

Isaiah 9:6-7

"For a child will be born to us, a son will be given to us;
And the government will rest on His shoulders
And His name will be called Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God,
Eternal Father, Prince of Peace.
There will be no end to the increase of His government or of peace,
On the throne of David and over his kingdom"

Isaiah 11:1-4

"Then a shoot will spring from the stem of Jesse,
And a branch from his roots will bear fruit.
And the Spirit of the LORD will rest on Him, ...
And He will strike the earth with the rod of His mouth,
And with the breath of His lips He will slay the wicked."

Isaiah 11:9

"For the Earth will be full of the knowledge of the LORD
As the waters cover the sea."

Isaiah 26:19

"Your dead will live;
Their corpses will rise.
You who lie in the dust, awake and shout for joy,
For your dew is as the dew of the dawn,
And the earth will give birth to the departed spirits." (Reincarnation)

Isaiah 42:1-3

"Behold, My Servant, whom I uphold;
My chosen one in whom My soul delights.
I have put My Spirit upon Him;
He will bring forth justice to the nations.
He will not cry out or raise His voice,
Nor make His voice heard in the street.
A bruised reed He will not break,
And a dimly burning wick He will not extinguish;
He will faithfully bring forth justice."

Isaiah 43:15

"I am the LORD, your Holy One,
The Creator of Israel, your King."

Isaiah 53:10

"But the LORD was pleased
To crush Him, putting Him to grief;
If He would render Himself as a guilt offering, ...
Therefore, I will allot Him a portion with the great,
and he will divide the booty with the strong;
Because He poured out Himself to death,
And was numbered with the transgressors;
Yet He Himself bore the sin of many,
And interceded for the transgressors." (Jesus)

Isaiah 65:17 "For behold, I create new heavens and a new earth."

Jeremiah 17:10

"I, the LORD, search the heart,
I test the mind,
Even to give to each man according to his ways,
According to the results of his deeds." (reaper)

Jeremiah 23:5-6

"Behold, the days are coming," declares the LORD,
'When I shall raise up for David a righteous Branch;
And He will reign as king and act wisely
And do justice and righteousness in the land.
In His days Judah will be saved,
And Israel will dwell securely;
And this is His name by which He will be called,
The LORD our righteousness.'"

Jeremiah 31:34 "And they shall not teach again, each man his neighbor and each man his brother, saying,
'Know the LORD,' for they shall all know Me, from the least of them to the greatest of them"

Jeremiah 33:15 "I will cause a righteous Branch of David to spring forth; and He shall execute justice
and righteousness on the earth."

Daniel 3:19-27 "He [Nebuchadnezzar] answered by giving orders to heat the furnace seven times more than
it was usually heated. And he commanded certain valiant warriors who were in his army to tie up
Shadrach, Meshach and Abed-nego, in order to cast them into the furnace of blazing fire. ... the fire had
no effect on the bodies of these men nor was the hair of their head singed, nor were their trousers
damaged, nor had the smell of fire even come upon them."

Daniel 7:13-14

"I kept looking in the night visions,
And behold, with the clouds of heaven
One like a Son of Man was coming,
And He came up to the Ancient of Days
And was presented before Him.
And to Him was given dominion,
Glory and a kingdom,
That all the peoples, nations, and men of every language
Might serve Him.
His dominion is an everlasting dominion
Which will not pass away;
And His kingdom is one
Which will not be destroyed."

Daniel 8:25 "Prince of princes"

Joel 2:28 "I will pour out My Spirit on all mankind"

Acts 9:3-7 "And it came about that as he journeyed, he was approaching Damascus, and suddenly a light from heaven flashed around him; and he fell to the ground, and heard a voice saying to him, 'Saul, Saul, why are you persecuting Me?' And he said, 'Who art Thou, Lord?' and He said, 'I am Jesus whom you are persecuting, but rise, and enter the city, and it shall be told you what you must do.' And the men who traveled with him stood speechless, hearing the voice, but seeing no one."

1 Corinthians 13:4-8 "Love is patient, love is kind, and is not jealous; love does not brag and is not arrogant, does not act unbecomingly; it does not seek its own, is not provoked, does not take into account a wrong suffered, does not rejoice in unrighteousness, but rejoices with the truth; bears all things believes all things, hopes all things, endures all things. Love never fails; but if there are gifts of prophesy, they will be done away; if there are tongues, they will cease; if there is knowledge, it will be done away."

Revelation 2:20 "But I have this against you, that you tolerate the woman Jezebel, who calls herself a prophetess, and she teaches and leads My bond-servants astray"

Revelation 5:5-6 "'the Lion that is from the tribe of Judah, the Root of David, has overcome so as to open the book and its seven seals.' And I saw between the throne (with the four living creatures) and the elders a Lamb standing, as if slain, having seven horns and seven eyes, which are the seven Spirits of God, sent out into all the earth."

Revelation 12:5 "And she gave birth to a son, a male child, who is to rule all the nations with a rod of iron; and her child was caught up to God and to His throne."

Revelation 12:7-9 "And there was war in heaven, Michael and his angels waging war with the dragon. And the dragon and his angels waged war, and they were not strong enough, and there was no longer a place found for them in heaven. And the great dragon was thrown down, the serpent of old who is called the devil and Satan, who deceives the whole world; he was thrown down to the earth, and his angels were thrown down with him."

Revelation 13:18 "Here is wisdom. Let him who has understanding calculate the number of the beast, for the number is that of a man; and his number is six hundred and sixty-six."

Revelation 19:6-7 "Hallelujah! For the Lord our God, the Almighty, reigns. Let us rejoice and be glad and give the glory to Him, for the marriage of the Lamb has come and His bride has made herself ready."

Bhagavad Gita 2:13 "As the embodied soul continuously passes, in this body, from boyhood to youth to old age, the soul similarly passes into another body at death. A sober person is not bewildered by such a change."

Bhagavad Gita 2:58 "One who is able to withdraw his senses from sense objects, as the tortoise draws its limbs within the shell, is firmly fixed in perfect consciousness."

Bhagavad Gita 11:32 "Time I am, the great destroyer of the worlds"

Tao 11:1-11 "We join spokes together in a wheel, but it is the center hole that makes the wagon move ... We work with being, but non-being is what we use."

IX. OMENS

The Bible is full of omens, and while skepticism and analysis are healthy, many modern readers discard them all as superstition. Surely ancient Romans were not intimate with the Bible, let us see if omens from independent sources agree.

Plutarch's Life of Fabius, regarding Hannibal:

"Besides the more common signs of thunder and lightening then happening, the report of several unheard of and utterly strange portents much increased the popular consternation. For it was said that some targets sweated blood; that at Antium, when they reaped their corn, many of the ears were filled with blood; that it had rained red-hot stones; that the Falerians had seen the heavens open and several scrolls falling down, in one of which was plainly written, 'Mars himself stirs his arms.' " [reaper, brimstone, scrolls]

"The friends of Hannibal earnestly persuaded him to follow up his victory, and pursue the flying Romans into the very gates of Rome, assuring him that in five days' time he might sup in the Capitol; nor is it easy to imagine what consideration hindered him from it. It would seem rather that some supernatural or divine intervention caused the hesitation and timidity which he now displayed, and which made Barcas, a Carthaginian, tell him with indignation, 'You know, Hannibal, how to gain a victory, but not how to use it.' " [foreshadowing]

Plutarch's Life of Marcellus, regarding Hannibal:

"And, truly, many other prodigies affrighted him; some temples had been struck by lightening, and in Jupiter's temple mice had gnawed the gold; it was reported, also, that an ox had spoken, and that a boy had been born with a head like an elephant's." [ox speaking, elephant head]

Plutarch's Life of Caesar:

"[Caesar's] soldiers were forced to dig up a kind of root which grew there, and tempering it with milk, to feed on it. Sometimes they made a kind of bread of it, and advancing up to the enemy's outposts, would throw in these loaves" [root, loaf]

"Fate, however, is to all appearance more unavoidable than unexpected. For many strange prodigies and apparitions are said to have been observed shortly before this event [Caesar's assassination] ... a number of men were seen, looking as if they were heated through with fire, contending with each other; that a quantity of flame issued from the hand of a soldier's servant, so that they who saw it thought he must be burnt, but that after all he had no hurt. As Caesar was sacrificing, the victim's heart was missing, a very bad omen, because no living creature can subsist without a heart. One finds it also related by many that a soothsayer bade him prepare for some great danger on the Ides of March. When this day was come, Caesar, as he went to the senate, met this soothsayer, and said to him by way of raillery, 'The Ides of March are come,' who answered him calmly, 'Yes, they are come, but they are not past.' The day before his assassination he supped with Marcus Lepidus; and as he was signing some letters according to his custom, as he reclined at table, there arose a question what sort of death was the best. At which he immediately, before any one could speak, said, 'A sudden one.' [fire unburnt, Ides, dictation]

After this, as he was in bed with his wife, all the doors and windows of the house flew open together; he was startled at the noise and the light which broke into the room, and sat up in his bed, where by the moonshine he perceived Calpurnia fast asleep, but heard her utter in her dream some indistinct words and inarticulate groans. She fancied at that time she was weeping over Caesar, and holding him butchered in her arms. Others say this was not her dream, but that she dreamed that a pinnacle, which the senate, as Livy relates, had ordered to be raised on Caesar's house by way of ornament and grandeur, was tumbling down, which was the occasion of her tears and ejaculations. When it was day, she begged of Caesar, if it were possible, not to stir out, but to adjourn the senate to another time; and if he slighted her dreams, that she would be pleased to consult his fate by sacrifices and other kinds of divination. Nor was he himself without some suspicion and fears; for he never before discovered any womanish superstition in Calpurnia, whom he now saw in such great alarm." [gates, dreams, pillar]

"But the great genius which attended him though his lifetime even after his death remained as the avenger of his murder, pursuing through every sea and land all those who were concerned in it, and suffering none to escape, but reaching all who in any sort or kind were either actually engaged in the fact, or by their counsels any way promoted it. [reaper]

The most remarkable of mere human coincidences was that which befell Cassius, who, when he was defeated at Philippi, killed himself with the same dagger which he had made use of against Caesar. The most signal preternatural appearances were the great comet, which shone very bright for seven nights after Caesar's death, and then disappeared, and the dimness of the sun, whose orb continued pale and dull for the whole of that year, never showing its ordinary radiance at its rising, and giving but a weak and feeble heat. The air consequently was damp and gross for want of stronger rays to open and rarify it. The fruits, for that reason, never properly ripened, and began to wither and fall off for want of heat before they were fully formed. But above all, the phantom which appeared to Brutus showed the murder was not pleasing to the gods. [reaper, comet, seven, sun, phantom]

... [Brutus] saw a terrible figure, like that of a man but of unusual stature and severe countenance. He was somewhat frightened at first, but seeing it neither did nor spoke anything to him, only stood silently by his bedside, he asked who it was. The spectre answered him, 'Thy evil genius, Brutus, and thou shalt see me at Philippi.' Brutus answered courageously, 'Well, I shall see you,' and immediately the appearance vanished. ... The night before the second battle, the same phantom appeared to him again, but spoke not a word. He presently understood his destiny was at hand, and exposed himself to all the danger of the battle. Yet he did not die in the fight, but seeing his men defeated, got up to the top of a rock, and there presenting his sword to his naked breast, and assisted, as they say, by a friend, who helped him to give the thrust, met his death." [phantom]

Plutarch's Life of Antony, regarding Caesar's revenge:

"These prodigies were said to have announced the war. Pisaurum, where Antony had settled a colony, on the Adriatic sea, was swallowed up by an earthquake; sweat ran from one of the marble statues of Antony at Alba for many days together, and though frequently wiped off, did not stop. When he himself was in the city of Patrae, the temple of Hercules was struck by lightning, and at Athens, the figure of Bacchus was torn by a violent wind out of the Battle of the Giants, and laid flat upon the theatre; with both which deities Antony claimed connection, professing to be descended from Hercules, and from his imitating Bacchus in his way of living having received the name of young Bacchus. The same whirlwind at Athens also brought down, from amongst many others which were not disturbed, the colossal statues of Fumenes and Attalus, which were inscribed with Anthony's name. And in Cleopatra's admiral galley, which was called the Antonias, a most inauspicious omen occurred. Some swallows had built in the stern of the galley, but other swallows came, beat the first away, and destroyed their nests." [earthquake, whirlwind, birds]

X. TELEPATHY

We have proven the LORD of the Old Testament is telepathic, for how else did He inspire etymologies? Prime Biblical examples are the Prophets and hardening Pharaoh's heart in Exodus. Thus we may reasonably postulate that the Son of God has similar telepathic ability. Indeed this is non-corporeally confirmed in the Acts of the Apostles, written in Greek not Hebrew, where Saul hears a voice but sees no one, and is subsequently transformed from a rabid anti-Christian to the apostle St. Paul. Doubting the narrative, a skeptic may yet doubt G's telepathy. But the veracity of Saul's complete change of character and faith is not in doubt, as his behavior is well documented.

Having established reincarnation, we can examine the historical record for evidence of corporeal telepathy. All the lives of G stand in evidence, with Cleopatra the prime example. Mark Antony, a career soldier styling himself young Bacchus, is completely transformed into a love crazed lunatic, similar to St. Paul. Note that this change is recorded independent of the Biblical tradition. Consistency of powerful influence beyond possible natural ability proves telepathy. And what is love, the Greeks distinguished eight different types?

From Plutarch's Life of Antony:

"In fine, they so melted and unmanned him [Anthony] that, fully believing she [Cleopatra] would die if he forsook her, he put off the war and returned to Alexandria, deferring his Median expedition until next summer, though news came of the Parthians being all in confusion with intestine disputes."

"Cleopatra, jealous of the honours Octavia had received in Athens (for Octavia was much beloved by the Athenians), courted the favor of the people with all sorts of attentions. ... He [Antony] sent orders to Rome to have Octavia removed out of his house. She left it, we are told, accompanied by all his children, except the eldest by Fulvia, who was then with his father, weeping and grieving that she must be looked upon as one of the causes of the war. The Romans pitied, not so much her, as Anthony himself, and more particularly those who had seen Cleopatra, whom they could report to have no way the advantage of Octavia either in youth or in beauty."

"As soon as Caesar [Augustus] had completed his preparations, he had a decree made declaring war on Cleopatra, and depriving Anthony of the authority which he had let a woman exercise in his place. Caesar added that he had drunk potions that had bereaved him of his senses, and that the generals they would have to fight with would be Mardion the eunuch, Pothinus, Iras, Cleopatra's hair-dressing girl, and Charmion, who were Antony's chief state-councillors."

"But so wholly was he [Anthony] now the mere appendage to the person of Cleopatra that, although he was much superior to the enemy in land forces, yet, out of compliance to his mistress, he wished the victory to be gained by sea."

"But the fortune of the day was still undecided, and the battle equal, when in a sudden Cleopatra's sixty ships were seen hoisting sail and making out to sea in full flight, right through the ships that were engaged. For they were placed behind the great ships, which, in breaking through, they put into disorder. The enemy was astonished to see them sailing off with a fair wind towards Peloponnesus. Here it was that Antony showed to all the world he was no longer actuated by the thoughts and motives of a commander or a man, or indeed by his own judgement at all, and what was once said as a jest, that the soul of a lover lives in some one else's body, he proved to be a serious truth. For, as if he had been born part of her, and must move with her wheresoever she went, as soon as he saw her ship sailing away, he abandoned all that were fighting and spending their lives for him, and put himself aboard a galley of five banks of oars, taking with him only Alexander of Syria and Scellias, to follow her that had so well begun his ruin and would hereafter accomplish it."

"Only a few had known of Antony's flight; and those who were told of it could not at first give any belief to so incredible a thing as that a general who had nineteen entire legions and twelve thousand horse upon the seashore, could abandon all and fly away; and he, above all, who had so often experienced both good and evil fortune, and had in a thousand wars and battles been inured to changes. His soldiers, however, would not give up their desires and expectations, still fancying he would appear from some part or other, and showed such a generous fidelity to his service that, when they were thoroughly assured that he was fled in earnest, they kept themselves in a body seven days, making no account of the messages that Caesar sent to them."

"He [Antony] retired into the city, crying out that Cleopatra had betrayed him to the enemies he had made for her sake. She [Cleopatra] being afraid lest in his fury and despair he might do her a mischief, fled to her monument, and letting down the falling doors, which were strong with bars and bolts, she sent messengers who should tell Antony she was dead. He, believing it, cried out, "Now, Antony, why delay longer? Fate has snatched away the only pretext for which you could say you desired yet to live." ... and so he ran himself into the belly, and laid himself upon the couch. The wound, however, was not immediately mortal. ... When he understood she was alive, he eagerly gave order to the servants to take him up ... Those that were present say that nothing was ever more sad than this spectacle, to see Antony, covered all over with blood and just expiring, thus drawn up, still holding up his hands to her, and lifting up his body with the little force he had left. As, indeed, it was no easy task for the women; and Cleopatra, with all her force, clinging to the rope, and straining with her head to the ground, with difficulty pulled him up, while those below encouraged her with their cries, and joined in all her efforts and anxiety. When she had got him up, she laid him on the bed, tearing all her clothes, which she spread upon him; and, beating her breast with her hands, lacerating herself, and disfiguring her own face with the blood from his wounds, she called him her lord, her husband, her emperor, and seemed to have pretty nearly forgotten all her own evils, she was so intent upon his misfortunes."

"And in the end, like another Paris [and Helen] he [Antony] left the battle to fly to her arms; or rather, to say the truth, Paris fled when he was already beaten; Antony fled first, and, following Cleopatra, abandoned his victory."

"There was no law to prevent Demetrius from marrying several wives; from the time of Philip and Alexander it had become usual with Macedonian kings, and he did no more than was done by Lysimachus and Ptolemy. And those he married he treated honourably. But Antony, first of all, in marrying two wives at once, did a thing which no Roman had ever allowed himself; and then he drove away his lawful Roman wife to please the foreign and unlawful woman. And so Demetrius incurred no harm at all; Antony procured his ruin by his marriage."

XI. CONCLUSIONS

By repetition we see Muhammad was an archangel not a prophet, yet he brought many people closer to the LORD. Thus the Bible is a better reference than the Quran. By the names of sources Q, L, and M, we conclude much of the New Testament is derived from the Old. For example, the Parable of Jesus and the Devil is really God and the Devil, similar to the book of Job. By etymologies we see Jesus was the Son of God not the Messiah, yet He brought many people closer to the LORD. The validity of reincarnation and its pattern implies Jesus was somewhat less than the paragon of virtue. Examining the word "chime" proves the Eucharist a valid sacrament. The Old Testament implies a divine right to Israel for righteous people of Hebrew descent.

We extrapolate by coincidence. The onset of World War I, the assassination of Archduke Franz Ferdinand, being in the pathway of a 19 year old twice, is an act of the LORD. World War II and the Holocaust are linked to the atrocities committed by Khazarian Jews in Eastern Europe prior, namely ethnic genocide in Russia and mass starvation in Ukraine. Historical editing is a common tactic. Atlantis did exist, it was called Aztlán, the homeland of the Aztecs. Extraordinary omens have meaning, Coronavirus among them.

A clearly benevolent Creator implies an explorable universe, not perpetual tantalizing, so we conjecture the unification of physics will lead to the exploration of space. For an elegant ontological proof of the LORD, see St. Anselm.

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XIII. IMAGES

(following pages)

Image 1 - Om Namo Narayana

Image 2 - Buddha

Image 3 - Infinite

Image 4 - Father and Son

Image 5 - Whirlwind

Image 6 - Genie of Lambda

Flex
2/23/6

Image 7 - El of Biblos

Gandalf
Auritus
6/17/15

Image 8 - Gandalf

flis

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Image 9 - Akira

6/24/16
a. flex

Image 10 - Q and G

M 1

Water

Mata

M 3

M 5

